

The Influence of Professional Identity and Teamwork Skills on the Teacher Behavior of Public Elementary School Teachers

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the extent of influence of teacher behavior. Specifically, it established the interrelationship among the professional identity, teamwork skills and teacher behavior of selected private schools in San Isidro District. Quantitative research design were utilized in this study. The data were gathered from the 300 teachers of selected schools in San Isidro District.. There were three sets of survey questionnaires used in data gathering. Findings revealed that the level of professional identity, teamwork skills and teacher behavior, were rated very high. There were significant relationships between professional identity and teacher behavior and teamwork skills and teacher behavior. Conclusive statements were drawn based on the findings of the study; the level of professional identity is high level. teamwork skills and teacher behavior correspondingly is very high respectively. On the other hand, there were significant relationships between the exogenous variable and teacher behavior.

Keywords:- Education, teacher behavior, schools, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Change is everywhere. The changes of today threatened teachers and lead to the engagement of behaviors that may cause misconduct. It may conserve the ego of the teacher but there are resistances made from policies, laws and even the norms of the society. Some teachers give up easily when they face problems and difficulties in the teaching learning process and leads to less effectivity in teaching. Efficient teachers typically have high student accomplishment, whereas teachers with low efficiency typically have low student achievement. This is due to the range of more effective and positive teaching methods. (Ashton & Webb, 1986; Bandura, 1997 & Gregoire, 2019).

Teachers' behaviors are regarded as some of the most significant environmental characteristics that might support students' effort or involvement in learning tasks and assist learners in developing good attitudes toward learning. Due to this, second language motivation research heavily emphasizes the function of teachers in boosting language learners' motivation and lowering their level of demotivation. (Dee, & Sievertsen, 2018).

A teacher's identity includes not just their own knowledge and behavior, but also their ideological, political, and cultural interests as well as their relationships with their students and the environment in which they live and work. Setting rules, explaining consequences, and giving the customary advice on motivating pupils and fostering connections are just the beginning of teaching behavior.. (Demaray, 2010).

Teachers' professional identity until now, no studies existed which related teachers' sense of their professional identity to specific effective teaching behaviours. (Lee, & Nie, 2014). The researcher has not come across a study that dealt on professional identity of teacher and teamwork skills on teacher's behavior in the local setting. It is in this context that the researcher is interested to determine whether the professional identity and teamwork skills that influences teacher behavior as this can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study especially the Department of Education and possibly develop action plans to improve school administration, thus, the need to conduct this study.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Professional identity of Teachers

An emerging research area that is getting more and more attention is teacher professional identity. This is hardly surprising, but the concept of teacher professional identity acknowledges the complexity of the teaching profession by taking into account both the personal and professional aspects of it, our understanding of teacher professional learning by recognizing that learning is directed both internally and externally, and that one's personality has a significant impact on professional development or learning. People's perceptions of themselves as teachers and the type of teachers they aspire to be are commonly used to determine professional identity.. (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011).

Research on teacher learning and development must comprehend the professional identity of teachers who are committed to implementing and maintaining inquiry-based learning in their practice, as schools are increasingly incorporating problem-centered, inquiry-based pedagogy to develop student productive knowledge and higher-order competencies (such as creativity, collaboration, and other 21st century competencies). (Fishman, Davis, & Chan, 2016).

The first domain is on engagement behaviors. Currently, Teacher behavior has been studied extensively, resulting in multiple review studies and meta-analyses in this field. International research in primary education has revealed that the following teaching behaviors are related to higher pupil accomplishment and participation, including effective classroom management, establishing a secure and engaging learning environment, giving clear instructions, giving feedback, adapting instruction, and teaching learning strategies. (Soubelet, & Salthouse 2015; Hanes & Norlin, 2017).

To understand and capture these behaviors, researchers They used outside observers to monitor teachers while they were teaching, and they asked students about their impressions of their teachers' conduct (Gnams, & Stiglbauer 2019). They also asked teachers about their own perceptions of their own teaching practices. The characteristics of a teacher's professional identity, such as dedication to their job, self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and motivation, have been found to be correlated with effective teaching practices and teacher effectiveness when examined separately. (Healey & Hays, 2012; Puglia, 2018).

The second domain is on knowledge of the profession. To meet the requirements of their pupils in the context of their educational environments, teachers rely on a body of professional knowledge and research. Instructors have a thorough understanding of their pupils' varied language, cultural, and religious backgrounds. They are aware of the impact that students' prior experiences have on their current learning. They are adept at structuring their lectures to accommodate pupils' differing levels of physical, social, and intellectual development and personality traits (Fletcher, 2013).

Also, knowledge building is a social activity system that is dynamic and encourages student interaction with a variety of viewpoints and ideas in order to develop the class's collective knowledge. A principle-based, adaptive approach to classroom design and practice is required due to the social and cognitive complexity of this process, as opposed to procedure-based inquiry designs, which call for students and their teacher to work on pre-defined project tasks while adhering to pre-scripted procedures and timelines (Zhang et al., 2020).

The third domain is on philosophy of the profession. Teacher is a key figure in the implementation of reforms in greater learning. The most effective strategies to successfully manage educational reforms can result from pedagogical research into the professional identity of the teacher, her/his priority values, self-evaluation of performances and professional knowledge, and how she/he conceptualizes the profession at an individual level. (Zheng, & Goldberg, 2018).

One of these elements is the teacher's personality in secondary or higher education (Vedel, & Andersen, 2020). The PI of a teacher is a complex, dynamic wholeness that emerges from the interaction of one's own and others' ideas of what it is to be a teacher, as well as from social and individual expectations (Goodson, Cole 2014).

Identification is defined as 'an active process that reflects an individual's ideas about himself and his own development. The ability to perceive one's life as an experience of the continuous unity of consciousness, the integrity of life objectives and daily behaviors, actions, and their meanings, which makes it possible to act consistently, is accompanied by the sense of continuity, coherence, and qualitative certainty. (Plieninger, & Heck, 2018).

The fourth domain is on behavior. Professional identity in terms of their attitude supported Noble's (2019) assertion that teachers' attitudes help raise students' levels of educational behavior and their foundation of more optimistic views of themselves and their institutions by cultivating students' passionate needs and demonstrating respect, care, and friendship.

In a similar spirit, professionals who have a strong sense of their professional identity are eager to share their knowledge, admiration, and enthusiasm for their field with others. They are also willing to speak out about it. They added that professionals with a strong sense of who they are and the professionalism that results from it will display their pride in their work by defending it against falsehoods.. Quin (2017) also stated that feelings of pride for the profession are the basis of professional identity (Remley & Herlihy, 2014).

The next domain is on professional roles and expertise. A career develops on a corpus of information and abilities that are specific to it and are typically not known to the general public. By helping teachers increase their pedagogical and mathematical expertise, instructors may have a big impact as leaders. Daily teacher assistance can be very important to a teacher's job, including conversations in the hall, in-classroom coaching, and frequent departmental and grade-level seminars on how kids learn mathematics. (Antunes-Alves, 2010).

The fifth domain is on philosophy of the profession. Creating a pleasant learning environment by appreciating and supporting intellectual variety is the single most essential thing a teacher can do to aid students in developing their critical thinking abilities. Students can freely express their thoughts with their peers and the teacher as a result, setting an example for other students to follow. A deeper comprehension of how diversity manifests both inside and outside of the classroom is necessary for respecting and encouraging intellectual diversity. One way that intellectual variety is displayed in the pupils' diverse world views (Healey & Hays, 2011; Remley & Herlihy, 2017).

The sixth domain is on professional values. The development of professional values, attitudes, behaviors, and self-identity components in the interpersonal aspect of identity development, on the other hand, are socialization processes that include the acquisition of a specific body of knowledge and skills necessary to achieve a new professional role. (Mellin, Hunt, & Nichols, 2017).

According to this model, new professionals learn the language, understand the norms, and adapt to the new professional culture through instruction, observation, practice, supervision, and consultation. An individual acquires acceptable professional ideals, attitudes, methods of thinking, and problem-solving techniques through the sociological process of immersion in a profession's culture. (Gibson, Dollarhide, & Moss, 2010).

The literature focuses on teachers' perceptions of their personal and professional selves. It speaks more directly to the crucial signs of this identity. The main objective is to advance our understanding of teacher professional identity and the variables influencing teachers' views of this identity. The study examines how well teacher identity profiles may be identified, how they link to instructors' ideas or beliefs about teaching and learning, and how they relate to their actual teaching behavior.

B. Teamwork Skills

In many schools, teachers labor in isolation, school administrators try to complete tasks on their own, and it is up to the individual to put new ideas into practice. Working as a team, however, is frequently a more efficient approach to complete significant jobs. Teamwork is therefore essential for the efficient and effective management of schools and a driving force behind educational advancement. In addition to the difficulties related to the implementation of the school, it appears that the lack of teamwork at schools in the has affected teachers' performance in the classroom and the standard of teaching and learning. (Greenwood, 2012; Phalane, 2018).

In the twenty-first century, the ability to work as a team has become essential. Internationally, a team's performance determines how successful a market is. Teamwork, however, has a long history. It is one of the oldest human practices still in use today and is not just limited to the corporate sphere. It's interesting to note that since the dawn of civilization, humans have collaborated in groups and teams. Working together leaves its mark practically everywhere. meanwhile, claims that the first official studies of collaboration were conducted during World War II and were primarily concerned with figuring out why military teams failed. (Grayson, 2018).

The first domain is on coordination. For an organization to be successful and profitable, teamwork is essential. Working in a team offers the benefit of allowing the workload to be shared across all team members, among other things. Working as a team also has advantages for the person, the team, and the company. Teamwork can be used to enhance the efficacy of the learning environment in schools. The majority of continuing professional development programs for teachers seem to give little formal attention to collaborative abilities (Phalane, 2016).

Collaboration is a resource that can be utilized to raise the standard of instruction and learning. This is seen, for instance, in team teaching, which encourages greater teacher interaction and may enhance the caliber of instruction and learning. Teachers' strengths are combined through cooperation. (Oster, 2012).

The second domain is on decision making. A second issue that frequently comes up in relation to school leadership is whether or which groups should have a role in decision-making in schools, along with how closely schools focus on teaching and learning. Having teachers play a significant role in leadership and decision-making within schools, especially outside of the classroom, has long been a goal of many school reformers. Expanding teacher roles in schools has become a focus of "teacher leadership" initiatives in recent years (Nielsen, 2019).

Collaboration, as demonstrated in team teaching, makes it easier for teachers to interact with one another, which may lead to better teaching and learning. The weaknesses of teachers are addressed while their strengths are integrated. Other team members can monitor, critique, and offer suggestions for change for underperforming teachers in a safe, encouraging environment. As a result, cooperation is important in businesses and improves work performance and outcomes, but it has a negative influence on teaching and learning in schools when it is lacking. (Potrebny, Wiium, &Lundegård, 2017).

The third domain is leadership. Effective schools almost always place a strong emphasis on key aspects of instructional leadership, such as fostering a culture of trust, respect, and teamwork within the building, encouraging high and consistent academic standards, providing objective, consistent, and useful evaluation of the quality of teachers and teaching, using evidence and data to make decisions about the instructional program, and a host of other factors (Jones ,2018).

The forth domain is interpersonal relationship. Many educators are unsure of how to help their kids emotionally prepare for life's challenges. One of these is the demand to conceal a secret from adults or other students. The benefits of building relationships and spending time with pupils cannot be replaced. The trust established during those occasions will assist pupils maintain emotional stability in a variety of circumstances. But, educators also think that educating students about situations where others may not have their best interests in mind is important. (Prinsley, &Baranyai, 2015).

Instructors would be wise to give their students knowledge of the strategies utilized by individuals who would want them to conceal a negative information. The following strategies are frequently combined and share similarities with one another. But, breaking them down into their individual components enables a youngster to comprehend them better, become resilient, and be prepared for anyone wishing to take advantage of them. Make the child feel guilty about potential consequences if the secret is discovered. (Garcia-Bayonas, & Gottschall, 2018).

The fifth domain is adaptability. If a person is unable to utilize all of his knowledge and abilities, none of the duties assigned to him will be completed with the high level of productivity that is necessary for every industry and serves as its primary goal. The employment chances nowadays are only available to those who are qualified and

have the potential to be exceptional workers because it is so difficult to get hired. (Arshad, 2017).

So, a workforce must be formed in order to fulfill the employer's aim to have abilities like effective communication, the capacity for decision-making, discipline, dedication, and technological proficiency. Based on these needs, specific skill education plays a significant role in generating highly talented and skilled pupils, adding to their academic abilities. This is meant to help students develop their soft skills, which are a combination of knowledge, abilities, and character traits that they must use and apply in their daily life. (Hashim, & Sidi, 2010).

The last domain is communication. The four forms of communication—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—should be mastered by teachers, and they should be able to use their skills in a classroom setting. It has been demonstrated that doing so influences both the teacher's personal professional performance and the academic success of the students. Since teaching itself entails communication, it is crucial to have these abilities when interacting with pupils. Your job requires you to understand and deconstruct difficult knowledge, communicate it to your pupils in a way that keeps their attention (both vocally and through written resources), and listen to and address any questions or issues they may have. (Lindblom-Ylänne, 2019).

C. Teacher of Behavior

The performance of the teacher leads to school climate that is good for pupils and students. As the teacher displays a harmonious attitude towards the learners, there is a possibility that greater learning is manifested. The result of assessment of the teacher to student impacts the teacher and it may result to teachers' effectivity in the classroom. Likewise, the diversity and differences of the classroom is a factor that stimulates teacher's efficacy in the teaching learning process. Additionally, teaching is a reciprocating doings, actions and reactions impact students and in the same way the students' measures and reactions influence the teacher. A comprehensible plan and philosophy on classroom organization is imperative (Raza, 2010; Levin & Nolan, 2014).

On the other hand, effective teachers put a stress on the instructions especially on academic as their goal, a major aim in the classroom (Borich, 2013). Likewise, classroom diversity, the activities in instructions, the participation of students and the suggestions and comments or what we call the feedback are very important in the motivation of the learner, or these are the driving forces that will push learners to learn more and direct their learning to a more procedural one (Ashton, 2010).

The first domain is on clarity. A teaching methodology used by teachers to avoid misconception on the topic presented to learners where there is a goal to achieve and that is to attain learners passing rate. The embodiment, but is not restricted to, such behaviors as clearing up course goals and reviewing and shortening course material. Similarly, most faculty in our study identified teaching clarity behaviors as significant in their courses with the least significant behavior to faculty, with the use of teaching

strategies to accommodate different way of learner's learning, still being reported as extremely or very important by more than 85 percent of the faculty in the sample (Akdeniz, 2017; Chesebro & McCroskey, 2001; Myers & Knox, 2001).

The second domain is on expression. Consequently, it seems rational to consider that classroom behavior of teachers might persuade students' drive to continue what has been started. They were driven with enthusiasm because teachers employ a more socially agreement to gain an increased communication between the learners. In the same mode, classroom organization matters when referring to manipulation on the learner's time to finish the task given or the minutes and hours they used up in learning. As the students are oriented with the pros and cons inside the classroom, there is a less misconduct on the classroom (Borich, 2018)

However, some teachers' commitment varies because different people have miscellaneous levels. Commitment is moderated to arrange of factors: some of which were supporting and some are withdrawing. The way teachers behave in the classroom depends on the climate or situation they are into. It relies on what attitude the environment they are into (Huberman, 2013).

The third domain is on interaction. Teachers' actions could in fact have some lasting unconstructive effects on students. It creates a great dissatisfaction towards the students resulting to passiveness in the interaction in the teaching learning process. Moreover, the way a teacher behaves in the classroom greatly impacts student's participation towards their peers (Sava, 2019).

On the other hand, the interaction between the teacher and learner can be seen on how the learners respond to the different activities they're involve in. Moreover, as the teacher interacts to its clientele, she sees to it that the learner mastered the lesson because after all it is the primary goal of the teaching learning process. The leader is the teacher where she is the facilitator and the mentor. The learners will be the one to create their own learning (Marchand-Martella, Blakely & Schaefer, 2019).

The fourth domain is on organization. As the class continues, it can be observed that a classroom that is organized is a classroom that is not topsy-turvy. Indicating specific places for materials like cartolinas, bondpapers, colored papers and portfolios have a great impact on teaching learning process. It is considered that as learners move in the classroom, they will not find it difficult to locate things because they knew where they can find it. Organization has a great impact for the reason that the overall physical appearance of the classroom motivates the learners to be present everyday and avoid frequent absences (Pascarella, Salisbury & Blaich, 2019).

The fifth domain is on pacing. An individual, a teacher, who masters pacing, is exceptional because as she plans her lesson for the day, she knows what activities to employ for her not to be overtime in her lesson delivery. It is noted that a subject or an area of a curriculum follows a

specific distribution of time to accomplish the content and the budget of work. Therefore, a wise decision of making pace a habit is good for the reason that a teacher can accomplish the lesson within the allotted time because if not other subjects will be affected (Akkoyunlu&Soylu, 2018).

The sixth domain is on disclosure. Disclosure implies very clear and complete regarding course requirements. When a teacher give suggestions, review learners on lessons especially when examination is fast approaching, give deadline reminders and stating of objectives is a manifestation of good disclosure (Higgins & Green, 2017).

Furthermore, disclosure implies very clear and complete regarding course requirements. When a teacher give suggestions, review learners on lessons especially when examination is fast approaching, give deadline reminders and stating of objectives is a manifestation of good disclosure. Moreover, storytelling is an effective way to let learners gain knowledge and this is also a display of disclosure (Downs, Javidi, & Nussbaum, 1988) to enhance student participation and to raise the percentage of emotional learning (Sorensen, 2019). Although Cayanus (2014) debated that disclosure must be use in a proper way. It must be in the welfare of the students' communication.

The seven domain is on speech. Seemingly, speech acts are significant marker of the communicative capability of our students because they stand fora great communication between the teacher and learner in the teaching learning process. It is best to use communication and speech in a proper way to lessen burden and annoyance. Pragmatic breakdown in intercultural communication may result in humiliation, hilarity, misunderstanding, or even indignation. The good news is that speech acts are now being presented clearly in many of the textbooks of dominant languages (Nelson & Knight, 2019).

Furthermore, building consciousness of speech acts can begin in the earliest days of language learning when students are performing greetings to their teachers and leave-takings, introductions, thank-you, and other simple social skills. At this point it can be distinguished that these actions are imbued with cultural content that identifies how, when, where and with whom these terms reused (Bagher, & Hossein, 2012).

The eight domain is on rapport. A sense of trust, open communication and good relationship is what we call rapport. It is important to have a good and harmonious relation towards learners because they are the key factor in the teaching learning environment. Similarly, despite the differences of each learner, they are unrestricted from a teacher's help and aid. If the teacher sees the learner having a hard time deciphering the idea or the knowledge it is best for her to help the learners to alleviate his difficulty. It is also best for the teacher to be objective rather than subjective. Everyone knows that every person is unique, therefore no one is the same, therefore an equal treatment must be observe (Umbach&Wawrzynski, 2005).

On the same manner, as the teacher give hints, prompt ideas and give time to answers to learners is an expectation from them that they can be competitive towards the goal. It motivates the learners to cooperate actively in class interaction because they know that were given a chance to prove their knowledge and their ability to answer questions especially higher order thinking skills questions. Moreover, it can be a student's way of expressing ideas without hesitations because they knew that they have enough time answering the queries given or thrown to them (Hativa, Barak, & Simhi,2011).

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D. Correlation between Measures

There is a significant connection between the three variables in which the professional identity relatively influences teacher behavior. The professional identity of teachers typically has to do with how they interpret their ongoing interactions with their setting in order to understand who they are as people. The argument made in this article is that this interaction shows up in teachers' job satisfaction, occupational commitment, self-efficacy, and change in motivation level. These constructs, which provide a personal perspective on how instructors regard themselves as professionals in their work, are frequently cited in the literature as being significant to teacher conduct. (Watt & Richardson, 2008).

In fact, it was brought up in a study by Crawford (2011) that claimed that teachers' concepts or images of themselves were related to their professional identities. It was asserted that these concepts or images of themselves heavily influenced how teachers taught, how they developed as teachers, and how they felt about curricular changes.

In a similar line, teachers' professional identities typically have to do with how they perceive their ongoing interactions with their setting in order to define themselves as instructors. This article makes the case that teachers' sense of their professional identity is the result of ongoing interactions between themselves and their environments. This sense of identity is demonstrated by teachers' job satisfaction, occupational commitment, self-efficacy, and shifts in motivational levels. (Day, 2002).

Identity as a professional means both a person and a setting. The professional identity of a teacher is not fully distinctive. Teachers are supposed to think and act professionally, but not just by adopting mandated information and attitudes; they are also expected to include personal traits (Gresham, 2004; Kurbanoglu& Akin, 2010).

Chang-Kredl & Kingsley (2014) also stress the dynamic character of professional identity, which is developed, built, and shaped throughout the course of a career. Depending on the value they personally place on these traits, teachers approach them in a variety of ways.

Vangrieken (2015) offers a thorough description of teacher collaboration in his philosophy. The team discovered that in order to promote effective teamwork, schools must provide a climate of trust, honesty, and respect. Successful teamwork also benefits from a culture of open communication and a shared sense of goals and values. Effective teams are also adaptable and take into account the individual members' expertise. The work is not imposed from the top down; rather, it results from collective group effort.

When educators work together, a project and the organization can benefit from the interests, backgrounds, and skills of each educator. This kind of teamwork fosters a higher feeling of accountability and trust, and it enables teachers to feel enthusiastic and confident about using their most innovative skills to enhance their schools (Moolenaar, 2016).

Learning comes from teaching, and one's outward action (performance) shows how much they have learned. The knowledge, abilities, and attitudes of team members make up their conduct when working together. Teamwork knowledge involves student knowledge and comprehension of team, environment, action, and program-related subjects (Nguyen et al., 2016).

According to Leonard and Leonard (2003), a poisonous school atmosphere makes it impossible for teacher collaboration to grow. Attrition rates in the teaching profession are rising globally as a result of a hostile climate and other stressors like low compensation, a lack of administration support, and unclear expectations. The foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures had helped bring into focus the importance on the influence of professional identity and teamwork skills on teacher behavior. The literature presented had also helped the researcher realize that professional identity and teamwork has a great influence on teacher behavior.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed the quantitative non-experimental design method of research using correlation technique. The plan and structure of this research was provide a credible answer to a research question. Its purpose is to describe obtainable characteristics such as success, attitudes, conduct, and connections. The present study is a good fit for the non-experimental quantitative method because it examines teacher conduct, teamwork abilities, and professional identity. Variables are only detected and analyzed as they exist in a natural environment; they are not altered in any way (Educational Research, 2011).

Descriptive survey is valuable in proving facts on which scientific judgments may be based. It offers crucial information on the nature of things and people and contributes significantly to the development of tools for measuring a variety of things, tools that are used in all forms of quantitative research as tools for data collection. Because it deals with the description and determination of both independent and dependent variables, the descriptive-correlational survey method is suited for the current inquiry (Creswell, 2013).

To determine the degree and kind of link between two or more variables, the correlational design is used (Creswell, 2003 as cited by Taylor 2018). The major impact of professional identity and teamwork abilities on teachers' conduct was examined and interpreted in this study to identify trends and patterns. Also, the study that uses statistical methods to examine the relationship between multiple independent variables and a single dependent variable also uses multi-regression analysis (Seda et al. 2020).

These findings were specific to the context of the public elementary schools of Municipality of San Isidro, Davao Oriental. The scope limits the possibility for the overall applicability of the results and the sample; accordingly, even though there could be common structures, the findings may not have overall applicability to other systems.

The public elementary schools of Municipality of San Isidro, Davao Oriental, were chosen as the research setting. The scope limited the possibility for the general applicability of the findings and the sample; accordingly, even though there could be common features, the findings may not have general applicability to other systems.

The respondents of the study were the selected 300 teachers in San Isidro North and South District of the Department of Education Region XI, Division of Davao Oriental. The respondents are determined using random sampling. The teacher-respondents are permanent in status, teaching any subject area. Further, the respondents were able to understand the content of the survey questionnaire and they had the capacity to interpret based on their experiences in the school setting. Below are the number of teacher-respondents of this study using universal sampling. The distribution of respondents according to schools under study are as follows:

The study was conducted on the first semester of School Year 2020-2021 in South District, Division of Davao Oriental. There were 300 teachers respondents, A Elementary School, 15 teachers; B Elementary School contributed a total number of 37 teachers respondents, 19 from C Elementary School, D Elementary School, 11 teachers, 16 teachers from E Elementary School, F Elementary School, 12 teachers, G Elementary School with 9 teachers, 10 teachers, H Elementary School, 10 teachers, I Elementary School, 10 teachers, J Elementary School, 9 teachers, K Elementary School, 9 teachers, L Elementary School, 19 from M Elementary School, 9 from N Elementary School, O Elementary School with 9 teachers,

15 teachers, P Elementary School, 7 teachers from Q Elementary School, 24 teachers, R Elementary School, 16 teachers from S Elementary School, T Elementary School with 16 teachers, U Elementary School with 9 teachers, and 9 teachers from V Elementary School. Moreover, the researcher considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. The teacher respondents are regular teachers among public elementary schools in San Isidro North and South District whose plantilla numbers are in the Department of Education. Teachers were willing to submit themselves and were permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey to be conducted. Teachers in high school were not included in the study. Those teachers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey, hence, teachers who clearly confessed their denial were excluded from the study. Further, the researcher considered teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires and those who want to withdraw will not be penalized.

There were three sets of questionnaire to be used in obtaining information on the conditions undertaken in the study. The instrument used in the study was adapted from the standardized survey of Woo & Henfield (2015) with minor revisions and to be submitted to the panel of experts for validation. The first set of questionnaire dealt with the influence of professional identity which focuses on engagement behaviors, knowledge of the profession, attitude, professional roles & expertise, philosophy of the profession, and professional values.

This instrument was presented to the panel of examiners then to the group of experts for validation of the items. The comments of experts shall be properly taken and incorporated in the finalization of the said instrument. The questionnaire used in the study was validated by the experts. It gained an over-all rating of 3.75 or very good. After the validation and modification, the experts approved the instrument. The questionnaire was contextualized and modified to suit the level of the respondents. Prior to the conduct of the actual survey, the researcher conducted a preliminary survey with 50 respondents, for reliability testing. The preliminary data gathered were subjected to an internal consistency type of validity test using Cronbach's alpha. With a reliability test of 100 items, the first independent variable resulted to have 0.904, second independent variable, the teamwork skills with 0.977, and the dependent variable resulted to have Cronbach's alpha of 0.974.

There would be modifications to check the validity of the questionnaires.

First, a letter of request were prepared duly signed by the researcher's adviser address to the Superintendent of the Division of Davao Oriental through gmail and google drive to allow the researcher to conduct the study among the teachers of the different public elementary schools in San Isidro North and South District, Division of Davao Oriental.

Moreover, the researcher made another letter to conduct the study to teachers in their respective schools in San Isidro North and South District. The researcher asked for approval from the School Heads to distribute survey questionnaire to their respective teachers. Upon approval of the request, the survey was then conducted.

Three districts based teacher trainers and one former teacher were given the survey to comment on its content and structure. For reasons of planning, the survey was simultaneously distributed among 315 teachers spread over 13 schools in the San Isidro. The teachers' e-mail addresses were retrieved from the websites of their schools. The schools that were selected are a representative sample of the different levels of elementary levels. Each teacher received, by e-mail, an invitation to participate. The survey was personalized by giving each participant a link in the e-mail with which s/he could enter the survey. If teachers did not want to participate, they were asked to reply to the mail, stating their reason for not participating, their age, gender, and total years of experience in teaching. Teachers who did not respond or who only partially completed the instrument were sent a reminder e-mail after two weeks. Of the 315 teachers approached, 300 completed the survey. Finally, the researcher tallied and tabulated all the data gathered from the respondents, subjected to statistical analysis. The statistical results were analyzed and interpreted.

The statistical tools that are employed by the researcher in the analysis and interpretation of the data are mean which was calculated by assigning values in a data. It is used in answering to the problem statements 1, 2, and 3. This tool is also employed to establish the professional identity, teamwork skills, and teacher behavior; Pearson r measured the level of the two variables divided by the product of their standard deviations. It is also used in measuring the level of relationship between the independent variables and sub-variables (professional identity and teamwork skills), and the dependent variable (teacher behavior). To determine which domain of professional identity and teamwork skills best influences teacher's behavior. And strengthen the obtained result.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis and interpretation of the acquired data are depicted in this part of the paper based on the research objectives of this study.

The flow of presentation on the stated topic is as follows: level of professional identity, level of teamwork skills on teacher, and level of teacher behavior, correlation between professional identity and teacher behavior.; correlation between teamwork skills and teacher behavior.

Table 1 shows the level of professional identity in terms knowledge of the engagement behaviors, knowledge of the profession, attitude professional roles & expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values and interaction which is the first objective of the study. As shown, the overall mean score of the level of professional identity is 4.34 with a computed standard deviation of 0.32 which is described as very high.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Engagement Behaviors	0.34	4.21	Very High
Knowledge of the Profession	0.41	4.50	Very High
Attitude	0.44	4.39	Very High
Professional Roles & Expertise	0.41	4.48	Very High
Philosophy of the Profession	0.39	4.33	Very High
Professional Values	0.37	4.12	High
Overall	0.32	4.34	Very High

Table 1: Professional Identity

This indicates that there is a need for teachers to have transparent sense of oneself that are vital for the counseling profession to prosper. This pertains to a set of beliefs, worth, and assumptions about different characteristics of an individual's chosen profession that distinguishes to other professions. In effect, Emerson (2010) added that the teachers should understand the pleasure of their subjects and curriculum. They grasp the basic concepts, structure and enquiry processes applicable to the programs they teach. matters most to them.

The second objective was to determine the level of teamwork skills which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators coordination; decision making; leadership; interpersonal skills; adaptability; and communication. Shown in Table 2 are the mean scores for the indicators of teamwork skills; . As shown, the overall mean score of the level of teamwork skills 4.41 or described as very high. This denotes that the respondent's is always observed.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Coordination	0.44	4.39	Very High
Decision Making	0.41	4.32	Very High
Leadership	0.45	4.34	Very High
Interpersonal Skills	0.43	4.60	Very High
Adaptably	0.43	4.27	Very High
Communication	0.42	4.57	Very High
Overall	0.35	4.44	Very High

Table 2: Teamwork Skills

In details, the indicator which has the highest mean score is interpersonal skills(4.60) or very high. It is followed by communication with a mean of (4.57) or very high. Finally, the indicator with the lowest mean score is adaptability with a mean of (4.27) still very high. The very high level for interpersonal skills and communication indicated that this conception was always observed.

The very high level of According to how respondents regarded a teacher's teamwork abilities, cooperation fosters a higher feeling of trust and accountability and gives instructors the confidence to contribute their most innovative skills to school progress. When teachers collaborate, they can assign tasks based on the personalities and areas of competence of each team member. The result is parallel to the idea of Rowman et al., (2013) that teamwork plays a major role in organizations and increases work performance and result in better outcomes Furthermore, this result is aligned with Lindblom-Ylänne (2010) thatThe four forms of communication—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—should be mastered by teachers, and they should know how to use their skills in a classroom setting. It has been demonstrated that doing so influences both the teacher's personal professional performance and the academic success of the students.

The third objective was to determine the level of teacher behavior. Presented in Table 3 are the results of teachers' behavior of the respondents. Computations revealed an over-all mean score of 4.21 or very high. The very high level could be attributed to the equally very high rating given by the respondents. The cited overall mean score was the result gathered from the computed mean scores of its indicators. It could be gleaned from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.45 or very high is disclosure. In contrast, indicator with the lowest mean rating of 3.81 or high is speech. The two highest indicators are disclosure with a mean rating of 4.45 and rapport with a mean rating of 4.40 or very high. Moreover, for disclosure, the highest items were reminding students of test dates or assignment deadlines and attending to teacher's instructions and advising students as to how to prepare for tests or exams. For rapport, the two highest items addressing individual students by name and offering to help students with problemsThe very high level of teacher behavior, as rated by the respondents, indicates that teacher's objectivity play an important role in the teaching learning process because as mentor with good disclosure gives samples of questions for the exams, reminds learners of deadline of their projects and assignments, and review set of objectives and subject matter for the betterment of the lesson.

The result coincides with the concept of Umbachand Wawrzynski (2005), cited that teacher expectations and evaluations are directly linked to achievement. No matter the skill level or natural ability of the student, all students have the ability and desire to succeed.

The result is connected to the views of varios authors Nelson et al., (2012) which emphasized that speech acts are important marker of the communicative competence of our students because they represent ways on how moments will be communicated especially on their own language. Especially, nowadays, learners are very diverse in language. A teacher must blend to the way the learners learn or else the purpose of imparting ideas to learners will be defeated and that is what we call the language barrier. Therefore, speech is very important in communications.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Clarity	0.440	4.37	Very High
Enthusiasm	0.388	4.17	High
Interaction	0.382	4.29	Very High
Organization	0.445	4.32	Very High
Pacing	0.366	3.89	High
Disclosure	0.446	4.45	Very High
Speech	0.345	3.81	High
Rappor	0.459	4.40	Very High
Overall	0.289	4.21	Very High

Table 3: Level of Teacher Behavior

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether or not the professional identity is significantly related with their level of teacher behavior.

Results of the computations are shown in Table 4. As shown in table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of professional identity and teacher behavior is .640 with the probability value of $p < 0.01$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship between the professional identity and teacher behavior.

Hence, the null hypothesis is being rejected. All indicators of professional identity when correlated with the overall and teacher behavior all of the R values where greater than $p < 0.05$ significant level hence, significant.

The present study reveals a significant relationship between professional identity and teacher behavior. This implies that teachers discipline style influences the teacher behavior which can be seen on the data. This confirms the study of Watt and Richardson (2008) which mentioned that if teachers' professional identity generally pertains to how teachers see themselves based on their interpretations of their continuing interaction with their context. It is argued here that this interaction manifests itself in teachers' job satisfaction, occupational commitment, self-efficacy and change in the level of motivation.

These findings support Newsom Crawford (2011) which stated that professional identity was related to teachers' concepts or images of self and it was argued that these concepts or images of self strongly determine the way teachers teach, the way they develop as teachers, and their attitudes towards educational changes

Professional Identity	Teacher Behavior							
	Clarity	Enthusiasm	Interaction	Organization	Pacing	Disclosure	Speech	Rappor
Engagement Behavior	.396* (0.000)	.279* (0.000)	.281* (0.000)	.366* (0.000)	.179* (0.002)	.251* (0.000)	.153* (0.008)	.181* (0.002)
Knowledge of the Profession	.431* (0.0000)	.341* (0.000)	.339* (0.000)	.422* (0.000)	.178* (0.002)	.475* (0.000)	.198* (0.001)	.384* (0.000)
Attitude	.538* (0.000)	.417* (0.000)	.339* (0.000)	.431* (0.000)	.162* (0.005)	.425* (0.000)	.200* (0.001)	.297* (0.000)
Professional Roles & Expertise	.420* (0.000)	.415* (0.000)	.341* (0.000)	.388* (0.000)	.148* (0.010)	.437* (0.000)	.245* (0.000)	.323* (0.000)
Philosophy of the Profession	.501* (0.000)	.439* (0.000)	.491* (0.000)	.536* (0.000)	.182* (0.002)	.558* (0.000)	.237* (0.000)	.368* (0.000)
Professional Values	.511* (0.000)	.399* (0.000)	.364* (0.000)	.474* (0.000)	.237* (0.000)	.460* (0.000)	.296* (0.000)	.284* (0.000)
Overall	.595* (0.000)	.488* (0.000)	.457* (0.000)	.556* (0.000)	.229* (0.000)	.557* (0.000)	.282* (0.000)	.394* (0.000)

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Professional Identity and Teacher Behavior

A. Significance on the Influence of Professional Identity and Teacher Behavior

Data shown in Table 5 is the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of the overall professional identity on teacher behavior. Using the Regression Analysis the data revealed that the overall professional identity significantly influence teacher behavior since the influence of professional identity on their teacher behavior has the F value 37.544 and p value less than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the professional identity significantly influence teacher behavior since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. The R2 value of .659 implies that 65.9 percent of the variance of professional identity can be attributed to the variance of teacher behavior while the remaining 34.1 percent were attributed to other factors not covered by the study.

It could be seen in the table that two out of six indicators of professional identity and significantly influence teacher behavior. However, philosophy of the profession, emerged as a significant predictor of teacher behavior, with p values of $p < 0.01$ and beta-coefficients of .292.

The overall result revealed that professional identity influences teacher behavior since it showed a positive result on the significance level which is higher than the boundary limit of 0.05. For further analysis, it indicates that philosophy of the profession influence teacher behavior which is conforms in the study of Crawford (2011) which stated that professional identity was related to teachers' concepts or images of self and it was argued that these concepts or images of self strongly determine the way teachers teach, the way they develop as teachers, and their attitudes towards educational changes.

Teacher Behavior				
Professional Identity	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant	1.627	.186	8.748	.000
Engagement Behavior	.085	.069	1.674	.095
Knowledge of the Profession	.069	.045	1.059	.290
Attitude	.104	.069	1.604	.110
Professional Roles & Expertise	.035	.025	.519	.604
Philosophy of the Profession	.292	.217	4.095	.000
Professional Values	.229	.179	4.000	.000
R	.659			
R ²	.435			
F	37.544			
p	.000			

Table 5: Significance Influence of Professional Identity on Teacher Behavior

B. Significance on the Relationship between Teamwork Skills and Teacher Behavior

Illustrated in Table 6 is the result of the test of relationship between teamwork skills and teacher behavior. Results of the computations the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of teamwork skills and teacher behavior is .681 with the probability value of $p < 0.01$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship between the teamwork skills and teacher behavior. Hence, the null hypothesis is being rejected. All indicators of teamwork skills when correlated with the overall and teacher behavior all of the R values were greater than $p < 0.05$ significant level hence, significant. Data revealed that the overall teamwork skills significantly influence teacher behavior since the influence of teamwork skills on their teacher behavior has the F value 51.734 and p value less than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the teamwork skills significantly influence teacher behavior since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. The R² value of .717 implies that 71.7 percent of the variance of teamwork skills can be attributed to the variance of teacher behavior while the remaining 28.3 percent were attributed

to other factors not covered by the study adaptably, emerged as a significant predictor of teacher behavior, with p values of $p < 0.01$ and beta-coefficients of .243.

The present study reveals a significant relationship between professional identity and teacher behavior. This implies that teachers discipline style influences the teacher behavior which can be seen on the data. This confirms the study of Watt and Richardson (2008) which mentioned that if teachers' professional identity generally pertains to how teachers see themselves based on their interpretations of their continuing interaction with their context. It is argued here that this interaction manifests itself in teachers' job satisfaction, occupational commitment, self-efficacy and change in the level of motivation.

These findings support Newsom Crawford (2011) which stated that professional identity was related to teachers' concepts or images of self and it was argued that these concepts or images of self strongly determine the way teachers teach, the way they develop as teachers, and their attitudes towards educational changes.

Teamwork Skills	Teacher Behavior								Overall
	Clarity	Enthusiasm	Interaction	Organization	Pacing	Disclosure	Speech	Rapport	
Coordination	.515* (0.000)	.472* (0.000)	.439* (0.000)	.548* (0.000)	.158* (0.006)	.493* (0.000)	.280* (0.000)	.382* (0.000)	.592* (0.000)
Decision Making	.571* (0.000)	.477* (0.000)	.375* (0.000)	.500* (0.000)	.205* (0.000)	.425* (0.000)	.204* (0.000)	.178* (0.002)	.526* (0.000)
Leadership	.541* (0.000)	.407* (0.000)	.339* (0.000)	.519* (0.000)	.184* (0.001)	.402* (0.000)	.221* (0.000)	.209* (0.000)	.507* (0.000)
Interpersonal Skills	.452* (0.000)	.388* (0.000)	.331* (0.000)	.394* (0.000)	.145* (0.012)	.387* (0.000)	.280* (0.000)	.272* (0.000)	.474* (0.000)
Adaptability	.607* (0.000)	.456* (0.000)	.386* (0.000)	.624* (0.000)	.280* (0.000)	.437* (0.000)	.328* (0.000)	.322* (0.000)	.616* (0.000)
Communication	.602* (0.000)	.435* (0.000)	.374* (0.000)	.536* (0.000)	.153* (0.008)	.536* (0.000)	.253* (0.000)	.345* (0.000)	.585* (0.000)
Overall	.678* (0.000)	.543* (0.000)	.463* (0.000)	.644* (0.000)	.231* (0.000)	.552* (0.000)	.324* (0.000)	.352* (0.000)	.681* (0.000)

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Teamwork Skills and Teacher Behavior

C. Significance on the Influence of Teamwork Skills and Teacher Behavior

Presented in Table 7 is the extent of influence predictor variables which are teamwork skills and teacher behavior. It was revealed that the F-value was 51.734 with a p-value of 0.000, which indicated that teamwork skills influences the teacher behavior of San Isidro District.

The result also displayed an R value of .717, with an R² value of .514 which meant that 51.4 percent of the variance of teamwork skills can be best explained by teacher behavior. The other 46.8 percent can be attributed to other variables not covered in this study. Among the indicators of teamwork skills emerged as the best predictor of adaptability given a higher Beta coefficient of 0.363.

D. The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Teacher Behavior

Data shown in Table 8 is the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of the overall professional identity and teamwork skills on teacher behavior. Using the regression analysis, the data revealed that the overall professional identity and teamwork skills significantly influence teacher behavior since the influence of professional identity and teamwork skills on their teacher behavior has the $p < 0.01$. This means that the professional identity and teamwork skills significantly influence teacher behavior. since the probability value is $p < 0.01$. The R² value of .508 implies that 50.8 percent of the variance of professional identity and teamwork skills can be attributed to the variance of teacher behavior while the remaining 49.2 percent were attributed to other factors not covered by the study.

However, teamwork skills emerged as a significant predictor of teacher behavior with beta-coefficients of .628

Teacher Behavior				
Teamwork Skills	B(Standardized Coefficients)	B(Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant	1.696	.152	11.154	.000
Coordination	.240	.158	4.055	.000
Decision Making	-.022	-.015	-.339	.735
Leadership	-.026	-.107	-.420	.675
Interpersonal Skills	-.016	-.011	-.266	.791
Adaptably	.363	.243	5.788	.000
Communication	.309	.213	5.063	.000
R	.717			
R ²	.514			
F	51.734			
p	.000			

Table 7: Significance Influence of Teamwork Skills and Teacher Behavior

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following suggestions are made in light of the facts and conclusion presented above. Thus, it is advised that the Department of Education establish programs or at the very least hold energizing seminars or workshops that would improve the behavior of the teachers. Teachers must collaborate as a team in order to strengthen their collaboration abilities. They can assign tasks based on the personalities and areas of competence of the team members.

The substantial relationship suggested that the policymakers, especially the Department of Education officials, examine and reread their current educational policies to determine if they address the needs and

challenges of being a 21st-century educator, primarily focused on how to heighten professional identity, hence, also improving their teacher behavior.

The significant relationship between teamwork skills to effect the and teacher behavior suggest that teacher if teachers work together successfully, group members must demonstrate a sense of cohesion. Researchers should explore differences among each group of educators relative to their years of teaching experience, stage of teacher development relationship with others. In an effort to enhance teacher behavior, it is essential for teacher educators, school administrators, and education professionals to determine specific practices to enhance teachers' perception of available support.

Teacher Behavior (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	B (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	1.307	.169	7.732	.000
Professional Identity (PI)	.308	.283	5.183	.000
Teamwork Skills (TS)	.457	.380	7.698	.000
R	.713			
R ²	.508			
F	153.296			
p	.000			

Table 8: The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Teacher Behavior

VI. CONCLUSION

The foregoing findings and conclusions give way to these recommendations. Consequently, the domains of professional identity also displayed results of very high in all indicators the engagement behaviors, knowledge of the profession, attitude professional roles & expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values and interaction. teamwork abilities. may maintain the extreme level. This might guarantee that when educators collaborate, they develop crucial personal and professional ties. Teachers frequently rely on one another for support and might assign tasks that make each feel effective. Cooperation among educators helps schools improve and students succeed.

Specifically in terms of clarity, expressiveness, interaction structure, tempo, disclosure, language, speech, and rapport, teacher behavior is also very high. In general, research suggests that professional identity and collaborative abilities have a big impact on how teachers behave. If teachers collaborate as a team, they can assign tasks in accordance with the personalities and areas of competence of each team member, potentially transcending the study's findings. This kind of teamwork fosters a deeper feeling of accountability and trust, and it gives teachers the confidence to use their most innovative skills to enhance their schools.

This is in line with Moolenaar's (2016) study, which suggested that when instructors collaborate, each teacher's interests, experiences, and skills can benefit the project and the organization. This kind of teamwork fosters a higher feeling of accountability and trust, and it enables teachers to feel enthusiastic and confident about using their most innovative skills to enhance their schools. Moreover, collaboration abilities predict teacher behavior.

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